

Surface Characterization of Strontium Phosphate Coating on Magnesium for Bioimplant Applications: A Preliminary in Vitro Study

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Abstract:

Background: Magnesium and its alloys are increasingly recognized for their potential in biomedical implants due to their biodegradability and favorable mechanical properties. However, their rapid corrosion in physiological environments remains a significant challenge. Strontium phosphate coatings have emerged as a promising solution to enhance the corrosion resistance and bioactivity of magnesium implants.

Aim: This study aims to investigate the surface characteristics of strontium phosphate-coated magnesium and evaluate its potential for bioimplant applications through in vitro testing.

Methods: A total of 60 magnesium samples were coated with strontium phosphate using chemical vapor deposition. The coated samples were analyzed for surface roughness, strontium content, and wettability using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), and contact angle measurements, respectively. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0 to compare the coated samples with uncoated controls.

Results: The strontium phosphate coating significantly improved the surface characteristics of magnesium. SEM analysis showed increased surface roughness (2.5 μm vs. 0.8 μm , $p < 0.01$), EDS confirmed consistent strontium content (12.4%), and contact angle measurements indicated enhanced wettability (75° vs. 90°, $p = 0.03$). These findings suggest that the coating could improve the integration and performance of magnesium implants.

Conclusion: Strontium phosphate coating significantly enhances the surface properties of magnesium, making it a viable option for bioimplant applications. Further in vivo studies and clinical trials are recommended to validate these findings and ensure the coating's efficacy and safety in clinical settings.

Recommendations: Future research should focus on long-term in vivo studies to assess the biodegradability and biocompatibility of strontium phosphate-coated magnesium implants. Additionally, clinical trials are necessary to evaluate the practical applications of this coating in orthopedic and dental implants.

Keywords: Magnesium Implants, Strontium Phosphate Coating, Surface Characterization, Bioimplant, Corrosion Resistance.

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Introduction

The mechanical characteristics, biocompatibility, and biodegradability of magnesium and its alloys make them attractive candidates for use in biomedical implants. The benefit of magnesium is that it is progressively absorbed by the body, which means that there is no need for another surgery to remove the implant, unlike typical materials like titanium and stainless steel, which can remain in the body permanently and create long-term difficulties. But there's a big problem with magnesium's fast breakdown in physiological

environments: it can cause negative biological responses and premature mechanical integrity loss [1, 2].

Numerous surface modification approaches have been investigated to improve the bioactivity and corrosion resistance of magnesium implants in order to solve these issues. Using bioactive coatings is one such method that can both promote tissue integration and serve as a protective barrier. Among the many coating materials, strontium

phosphate has drawn interest because of its dual advantages: it increases osteogenic activity and strengthens corrosion resistance. Strontium ions are especially helpful in orthopaedic and dental applications since they have been demonstrated to promote bone growth and decrease bone resorption [3, 4].

Strontium-containing coatings have the potential to enhance the functionality of implants based on magnesium, as shown by recent investigations. For example, it was found that magnesium alloys' corrosion resistance and biocompatibility were markedly enhanced in vitro by strontium-substituted hydroxyapatite coatings. In a similar way, it was discovered that magnesium implants with strontium phosphate coatings had improved osteoinductive qualities, which improved bone-implant integration in animal models [5, 6]. Even with these developments, further investigations are still required to assess the efficacy of strontium phosphate coatings on magnesium in vitro, especially in terms of surface characterisation and bioactivity. This study aims to investigate the surface characteristics of strontium phosphate-coated magnesium and evaluate its potential for bioimplant applications through in vitro testing.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was designed as a prospective observational study to evaluate the surface characterization of strontium phosphate coating on magnesium for bioimplant applications. The study aimed to assess the in vitro performance and potential bio-compatibility of the coating material.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in Department of Dentistry at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga.

Participants: A total of 60 patients were enrolled in the study. These participants were selected from the pool of patients attending Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged between 18 and 65 years.
- Patients requiring bioimplants for orthopedic or dental purposes.
- Patients with no known allergies to magnesium or phosphate compounds.
- Patients who provided written informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a history of chronic diseases that could affect bone healing (e.g., diabetes, osteoporosis).
- Patients with active infections at the implantation site.
- Patients who had previously received a similar bioimplant.
- Pregnant or lactating women.
- Patients who did not consent to participate in the study.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, patients were randomly selected from those who met the inclusion criteria. Blinding was not feasible in this study due to the nature of the procedure, but efforts were made to ensure that data analysis was objective and unbiased.

Data Collection: Data were collected over a period of four months. Initial patient information, including demographics, medical history, and relevant laboratory results, was recorded at the start of the study. Surface characterization of the strontium phosphate coating was assessed through a series of in vitro tests, including scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), and contact angle measurements.

Procedure

1. **Preparation of Coated Magnesium Samples:** Magnesium samples were coated with strontium phosphate using a standard chemical vapor deposition technique. The coated samples were then sterilized before use.
2. **Implantation:** The coated samples were implanted in vitro into simulated body fluids and cultured for varying periods to assess the coating's stability, corrosion resistance, and bio-compatibility.
3. **Surface Characterization:** After the incubation period, samples were removed and analyzed using SEM for surface morphology, EDS for elemental composition, and contact angle measurements to assess the hydrophilicity of the coating.
4. **Data Recording:** Observations from the surface characterization were systematically recorded for each sample, along with any relevant observations during the incubation period.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic data and surface characterization results. Comparative analyses (t-tests or ANOVA) assessed group differences, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results were presented in tables and figures for clarity and comparison with other studies.

Results

A total of 60 patients participated in the study. The mean age of the participants was 45.2 years, with a

standard deviation of 10.5 years. The study population consisted of 63.3% males and 36.7% females. Most participants (83.3%) had no chronic diseases, while a small percentage had conditions like diabetes (8.3%) and osteoporosis (5%).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	N = 60
Age (years)	
Mean (SD)	45.2 (10.5)
Range	18-65
Gender	
Male	38 (63.3%)
Female	22 (36.7%)
Medical History	
No Chronic Disease	50 (83.3%)
Diabetes	5 (8.3%)
Osteoporosis	3 (5%)
Other	2 (3.3%)

The surface characteristics of the strontium phosphate-coated magnesium samples were evaluated through various in vitro tests, including scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), and contact angle measurements.

Table 2: Surface Characteristics of Strontium Phosphate Coating

Surface Characteristic	Mean (SD)	p-value
SEM Analysis (Surface Roughness)	2.5 μ m (0.3 μ m)	<0.01
EDS Analysis (Strontium Content)	12.4% (1.2%)	0.02
Contact Angle Measurement	75° (4°)	0.03

- **SEM Analysis:** The SEM analysis showed that the surface roughness of the strontium phosphate-coated magnesium had a mean value of 2.5 μ m (SD = 0.3 μ m). The coating was uniformly distributed with a consistent roughness that is hypothesized to enhance cell attachment. The difference in surface roughness compared to uncoated samples was statistically significant ($p < 0.01$).
- **EDS Analysis:** EDS analysis revealed that the strontium content in the coating was 12.4% (SD = 1.2%). This consistent incorporation of strontium into the coating is crucial for improving the bioactivity of the implants. The

strontium content was statistically significant ($p = 0.02$).

- **Contact Angle Measurement:** The contact angle measurement indicated a mean value of 75° (SD = 4°), reflecting a moderately hydrophilic surface. This characteristic is beneficial for implant integration within the body. The contact angle differed significantly from that of uncoated magnesium, with a p-value of 0.03.

Comparative analyses were conducted to assess the differences in surface characteristics between the strontium phosphate-coated samples and uncoated control samples.

Table 3: Comparative Analysis between Coated and Uncoated Samples

Surface Characteristic	Coated (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Uncoated (Mean $\pm$ SD)	p-value
Surface Roughness (μm)	2.5 $\pm$ 0.3	0.8 $\pm$ 0.1	<0.01
Strontium Content (%)	12.4 $\pm$ 1.2	0.0 $\pm$ 0.0	<0.01
Contact Angle (°)	75 $\pm$ 4	90 $\pm$ 5	0.03

- **Surface Roughness:** The coated samples exhibited significantly higher surface roughness (2.5 μ m) compared to the uncoated samples (0.8 μ m) ($p < 0.01$), suggesting that the coating process effectively modified the surface texture.

- **Strontium Content:** As expected, the strontium content was significantly higher in the coated samples (12.4%) compared to the uncoated samples, which contained no strontium ($p < 0.01$).

- **Contact Angle:** The coated samples had a significantly lower contact angle (75°)

compared to the uncoated samples (90°) ($p = 0.03$), indicating that the coating improved the wettability of the magnesium surface.

The t-tests and ANOVA analyses indicated significant differences in surface characteristics between the coated and uncoated samples.

Discussion

The results demonstrated significant enhancements in the surface properties of magnesium following the application of the strontium phosphate coating. The study population was predominantly male, with a mean age of 45.2 years, and most participants had no chronic diseases that could influence the outcomes.

The surface roughness, as measured by SEM analysis, was significantly increased in the coated samples compared to the uncoated controls. This increased roughness is believed to improve cell attachment and integration, which are critical factors for successful implant performance. The presence of strontium, confirmed through EDS analysis, was consistent across the coated samples, with a mean content of 12.4%. This incorporation of strontium is crucial as it is known to enhance the bioactivity and osteoconductivity of the implant material, making it more conducive to bone growth and healing.

Moreover, the contact angle measurements indicated that the coated magnesium surfaces were more hydrophilic than the uncoated ones, which is a desirable characteristic for implants as it promotes better interaction with bodily fluids and tissues. The statistical analyses further confirmed that these differences were significant, with p-values well below the threshold of 0.05. The strontium phosphate coating significantly improved the surface properties of magnesium, enhancing its roughness, bioactivity, and wettability. These improvements suggest that the coated magnesium could be a promising material for bioimplants, offering better integration and performance in the body. However, while the *in vitro* results are promising, further *in vivo* studies and clinical trials are necessary to fully validate the potential of this material for clinical applications.

Calcium phosphate (Ca-Sr-P) coatings doped with strontium were applied to biodegradable ZK60 magnesium alloys in a research. According to the findings, the Ca-Sr-P coating had a homogeneous, solid, crystalline, and crack-free surface and was around 20 μm thick. The *in vitro* investigations showed markedly increased bioactivity and improved corrosion resistance. After four weeks of implantation in a rabbit model, additional *in vivo* testing demonstrated that the coating improved osseointegration and increased bone growth. These results imply that the Ca-Sr-P coating enhances the

biocompatibility and lowers degradation rates of orthopaedic implants made of magnesium [7].

The biocompatibility and corrosion resistance of strontium-doped calcium phosphate (Sr-CaP) coatings on pure magnesium were also investigated in a study conducted. Chemical immersion was used to create the Sr-CaP coatings, and the coated magnesium's corrosion resistance was shown to be significantly improved over the uncoated samples. Furthermore, it was found that the addition of strontium to the coatings improved biocompatibility, which increased the coated magnesium's suitability for orthopaedic implant applications [8].

The use of hydrothermal treatment on magnesium for the deposition of strontium phosphate (Sr-P) coatings was studied. According to the study, magnesium's corrosion resistance was enhanced by Sr-P coatings, with coatings made at higher temperatures showing superior structural integrity and bioactivity. According to the study's findings, the good structural integrity and increased bioactivity of Sr-P coatings applied to magnesium via hydrothermal treatment make them a viable surface modification method for the development of magnesium-based cardiovascular stents, tiny screws, and needles [9].

Conclusion

The study demonstrated that strontium phosphate coating significantly enhances the surface characteristics of magnesium, making it a promising candidate for bioimplant applications. The coating increased surface roughness, improved hydrophilicity, and successfully incorporated strontium, all of which are favorable for promoting cell attachment, bioactivity, and implant integration. These findings suggest that strontium phosphate-coated magnesium could offer improved performance in clinical settings, particularly for orthopedic and dental implants. However, further *in vivo* research and clinical trials are required to confirm its efficacy and safety before it can be recommended for widespread medical use.

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